

EXTENT OF COMPLIANCE OF MOTHERS TO SAFE MOTHERHOOD PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Maternal health remains a critical public health concern, with the Safe Motherhood Program playing a vital role in ensuring optimal care. This study aimed to assess mothers' compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program. It examined factors such as age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of children, number of prenatal check-ups, and the proximity of their residence to healthcare facilities. The researcher conducted the study in selected Level II hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan and administered a survey questionnaire to 60 mothers. A descriptive study approach was used, using statistical methods like frequency and percentage, weighted mean, ANOVA, t-test, and the Scheffe test. The respondents were predominantly young adults, married, holders of a Bachelor's degree, with an average monthly income, not working, and had a relatively low number of prenatal check-ups. Most respondents had an average number of children and lived near healthcare facilities. The findings revealed that mothers exhibited the highest levels of compliance in labor and delivery, health education, and counselling. Conversely, the lowest levels of compliance were observed in antenatal care and family planning. Significant variations in compliance were noted based on civil status, educational attainment, monthly family income, occupation, and the number of prenatal check-ups attended. Furthermore, the mothers' demographic profiles significantly influenced their overall compliance with the program. The researcher recommends adapting maternal health programs to enhance mothers' compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program outlined by the Department of Health.

Keywords: *Maternal Compliance, Safe Motherhood, Prenatal Check-ups, Public Health Program, Demographic Influences, Health Education*

INTRODUCTION

Maternal and neonatal mortality rates in developing nations, such as the Philippines, pose substantial obstacles, rendering maternal health a global public health concern. Pregnancy and childbirth-related factors cause difficulties or deaths annually in hundreds of thousands of women (Tulchinsky, 2023). Well-being during maternity requires total care during preconception, pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum. Good nutrition, a healthy lifestyle, good antenatal care, early detection and treatment of complications, and proper medical care are needed. The ultimate goal is to have a low-risk, full-term pregnancy, safe delivery of a healthy baby, and preservation of maternal health in the postpartum (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023).

The Safe Motherhood Program is a program that ensures the health of mothers before, during, and after childbirth and eventually reduces maternal and infant mortality rates. Compliance with the program is essential to achieve international and national health organizations' target goals. Various legal frameworks guide the Safe Motherhood Program in the Philippines to improve maternal health. Republic Act No. 10354 prioritizes maternal health care services, including family planning, competent attendance at delivery, and postnatal care (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). Maternal health service rights, an essential aspect of women's health (Philippine Commission on Women, 2009), are also protected by the Magna Carta of Women (Republic Act No. 9710) for women (Philippine Commission on Women, 2009), ensuring all women have a claim to improved, safe maternal and reproductive health service. In relation to global efforts toward the improvement of maternal and child health, the Department of Health (DOH) advocates the Maternal, Newborn, Child Health and Nutrition (MNCHN) Strategy (DOH, 2011).

The Philippine Department of Health (DOH) started the National Safe Motherhood Program (NSMP) to handle problems of maternal mortality and advance reproductive health in the nation, considering the severity of the mother health issue. This initiative conforms to the present mother and child health policies and legislation of the Philippine government. The State is required under Article II, Section 15 of the Philippine Constitution of 1987 to protect people's health and raise their level of knowledge of their health. (1987, Official Gazette). Moreover, the MNCHN Strategy is a reaffirmation of the country's commitment to providing high-quality maternal and neonatal health care (Department of Health, 2008).

The Safe Motherhood Program is built on four fundamental pillars: family planning, antenatal care (ANC), delivery and immediate postpartum care, and postnatal and newborn care. These pillars together form an integrated healthcare framework that provides safe pregnancy, safe childbirth and postpartum recovery and responds to preventable maternal and infant avoid (DOH,2020).

Family planning is an example of another important component of the Safe Motherhood Program, granting access to contraceptive and reproductive health education and counseling services to prevent unwanted conception. Family planning allows women the information they need to make decisions concerning birth spacing, fertility control, and reproductive well-being and prevents it from becoming a high-risk pregnancy and short birth space complication (United Nations Population Fund, 2021). It has been studied that when women are provided with access to contraception and quality reproductive healthcare, the rate of maternal deaths is greatly reduced, and neonatal health is improved (Gillespie et al., 2019). According to statistics, there is still a 14.4% unmet need for family planning services in the Philippines, despite tremendous progress since Republic Act 10354 was passed. Many women, especially those living in rural areas, do not have access to modern contraceptive techniques (UNFPA, 2023).

Antenatal care (ANC) forms the second pillar of the program, which forms a significant part of the program as it ensures that pregnant women receive routine prenatal check-ups, pregnancy-related complication screening, nutritional support, and medical interventions for the well-being of both the mother and fetus (World Health Organization, 2021). It empowers healthcare providers to diagnose potential health risks early, including gestational diabetes, hypertension, anemia, and fetal abnormalities, facilitating timely medical intervention (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023). With the goal of equipping women with the information they need for a safer pregnancy and delivery, ANC further promotes maternal education on immunizations, nutritional guidelines, skilled birth attendance, and healthy pregnancy practices (UNICEF, 2024). However, financial constraints, distance to health facilities, and lack of social support hinder a large number of Filipino women, especially those living in geographically isolated areas, from completing the recommended number of ANC visits (Sande, 2022).

The third component of the Safe Motherhood Program is delivery care, with pregnancy and delivery at facilities with skilled birth personnel to minimize risks (DOH, 2020). The three major causes of maternal death, including postpartum hemorrhage, obstructed labor, and infections, are often preventable and manageable with trained healthcare providers, midwives, and emergency obstetric services (WHO, 2021). Although the percentage of women giving birth in a healthcare facility has improved, the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) for the Philippines is still 128 deaths per 100,000 live births (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023) and is even higher for poorer rural areas.

Delays faced in seeking, reaching, and receiving emergency obstetric care are responsible for about 65 % of maternal deaths, especially among the indigenous and economically disadvantaged groups (Department of Health Services of Nepal, 2024). Strengthening the referral system in both local birthing centers and higher-level hospitals is another strategy to reduce maternal deaths (Pindani et al., 2021).

Given that access to emergency obstetric care, surgical procedures, and physiologic support during the labor and delivery process is critical for pregnant women, particularly those with high-risk pregnancies, the Safe Motherhood Program promotes facility-based deliveries in order to accomplish this (DOH, 2020). According to studies,

higher prevalence rates of facility-based births are associated with lower maternal and neonatal mortality rates as a result of managing complications that might arise during childbirth in a timely manner and increased access to skilled birth attendants (Pindani et al., 2021). Rural-urban disparities in maternal mortality remain a serious public health concern in the Philippines, where urban mothers suffer low risks for complications, while rural mothers are increasingly vulnerable due to the lack of health facilities (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023). Targeted interventions that address infrastructural, financial, and cultural barriers preventing women from seeking institution-delivery care are needed.

The last pillar, postnatal and newborn care, is about how mothers will recover, the health of newborns will be monitored, and essential newborn care will be provided. Postpartum is a highly vulnerable time for the baby and mother, and if there is no medical care, infections, postpartum hemorrhage, and mental conditions like postpartum depression can occur (Gonzalez & Kopparapo, 2022). The Safe Motherhood Program also offers mothers postnatal check-ups, mental health support, nutritional counseling, and postpartum family planning services that assist in their recovery and well-being (DOH, 2020). For instance, studies have shown that infants who breastfeed and are in direct contact with their mother tend to have a stronger bond than those who do not breastfeed, as well as less risk for type 2 diabetes, postpartum depression, and breast and ovarian cancer (National Institute of Health, 2020). Access to contraceptive services in the postpartum period also serves to space the interpregnancy intervals and prevent unintended births, leading to improved maternal and child health indices. (Sonalkar & Mody, 2025) Nonetheless, postnatal care is one of the least accessed of all maternal health services in the Philippines, especially in rural areas, where follow-up visits are frequently abandoned because of logistical issues, financial constraints, and insufficient knowledge (WHO, 2024). These obstacles must be addressed in order to make certain that improvements in mother and infant health outcomes are maintained.

Care after giving birth is essential for the well-being of mothers and their children. The postpartum period is a critical time to assess the health of both the mother and the newborn because of the potential complications, including postpartum hemorrhage, infection, and mental health issues. Comprehensive postnatal treatment includes postpartum mental health assessment, breastfeeding support, and contraception advice (Gonzalez & Kopparapo, 2022). Breastfeeding supports the growth, development, and wellness of an infant by providing nutrients and immunological support. Additionally, it has been connected to a lower prevalence of type II diabetes, ovarian and breast cancer, postnatal depression, and improved mother-infant attachment (National Institute of Health, 2020). Access to contraceptive services in the postpartum period also serves to space the interpregnancy intervals and prevent unintended births, leading to improved maternal and child health indices (Sonalkar & Mody, 2025).

In addition to these four pillars, the Department of Health (DOH) has identified ten essential components of the Safe Motherhood Program to ensure comprehensive maternal healthcare services. These components include pre-pregnancy counseling, antenatal care, the prevention and management of pregnancy-related complications,

facility-based deliveries, essential newborn care, postnatal monitoring, family planning, the management of reproductive tract infections, adolescent reproductive health education, and maternal health advocacy (DOH, 2020). Each of these outcomes contributes to strengthening the healthcare system's ability to tackle the issues of maternal health and reproductive rights and strengthen access to high-quality maternal and neonatal care.

Although the literature is abundant on maternal health policies, compliance and the critical role of institutions in enforcing such policies, local research, specifically examining the status of Eastern Pangasinan in its Level II government hospital facilities, is limited. Therefore, this study strives to fill that gap by exploring specific challenges mothers face in this region, barriers to complying with milk prescriptions, and recommending problem-based solutions. Ultimately, the study will help inform the development of effective evidence-based interventions that can enhance maternal and child health outcomes through understanding locally salient determinants of maternal health-seeking behaviors.

This study contributes to the knowledge by identifying determinants of compliance with maternal healthcare in the health, social, economic, and cultural domains. Incorporating these into the analysis will shed light on how policy, healthcare infrastructure, and individual circumstances interact and mutually constitute to mold maternal health behaviors in the Philippines.

Globally, WHO has formulated guidelines for maternal health with a focus on the practice of safe motherhood that includes access to skilled birth attendants, emergency obstetric care, antenatal and postnatal care, and policies to enhance maternal and neonatal health. (WHO, 2021) Antenatal care attended deliveries, emergency obstetric care, and postpartum care are all effective in reducing maternal and neonatal mortality. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs') Target 3.1, among others, mandates that the global maternal mortality ratio be fewer than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030 as part of their purpose to guarantee healthy life and promote well-being for everyone of all ages (United Nations, 2015). National programs, such as the Safe Motherhood Program in the Philippines, have been framed on these frameworks.

However, maternal mortality continues to pose a pressing public health problem. In 2020, as many as 287,000 women around the world died from pregnancy-related causes, many of which were preventable (WHO, 2024). Postpartum hemorrhage, infections, hypertensive disorders, unsafe abortion, and obstructed labor are the leading direct causes of maternal mortality, combined with indirect causes (e.g., anemia and malaria) (WHO, 2024). Most of these deaths can be attributed to the delayed search for care, delayed access to healthcare institutions, and unavailability of healthcare services, particularly in marginalized population groups (Department of Health Services of Nepal, 2024).

Across the globe, different studies indicate factors associated with compliance with maternal healthcare. Gillespie et al. (2019) stress that socioeconomic status, cultural

beliefs, accessibility of healthcare, and awareness are major determinants of adherence to programs about mental health. Similarly, the Safe Motherhood Initiative (SMI) has proven effective in reducing maternal deaths through the dissemination of protocols for obstetric emergencies. In the United States, hospitals in New York State have adopted guidelines for managing maternal sepsis, obstetric hemorrhage, venous thromboembolism, and severe hypertension in pregnancy (American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists, 2023). Similarly, research in Malawi demonstrates that 80% of maternal deaths can be prevented through community engagement and improved access to emergency obstetric care (Pindani et al., 2021).

There is a need to comprehend the context of compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program in the identification of gaps and developing strategies that can improve maternal healthcare services in the country. Because of these challenges, this study seeks to establish the level of maternal compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program, examine determinants of compliance, and establish evidence-based recommendations to improve maternal and child health outcomes. This study aims to identify barriers and close the gap in maternal healthcare services to contribute to an effective intervention for safer pregnancy, decreased maternal mortality, and better health of mothers and their babies.

The pandemic also highlighted the need for strong, functioning maternal health systems. Women who are pregnant or who have been diagnosed with or are suspected of having COVID-19 need comprehensive, quality antenatal, intrapartum, and postnatal continuous care and access to needed mental health support (Rana, 2020). The pandemic had a drastically devastating impact on maternal health outcomes due to the interruption of health services, necessitating robust and resilient maternal health programs.

In the Philippines, while the government has made considerable efforts to improve maternal health, gaps in the use of antenatal care (ANC) services have been reported. Sande (2022), in a study, concluded that women in Iriga City and Tabaco City have a number of barriers to antenatal care service use, including financial concerns, low-income family and social support, childcare requirements, and adverse experiences with health workers. This result is consistent with the broad investigations that indicate that the most crucial factors influencing mothers' healthcare-seeking behavior are socioeconomic status, education level, and access to health facilities (Rasheed & Alshuweim, 2023). The importance of maternal health education is also highlighted by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2024), which argues that women who receive antenatal care are better informed about healthy pregnancy behavior, warning signs during delivery, micronutrient supplementation, and immunization services.

A lot was done, but disparities in maternal health still exist, especially in rural and poor populations. DOH's National Safe Motherhood Program aims to enhance pregnancy and childbirth through increased access to emergency obstetric and newborn care (DOH Center for Health Development, 2020). However, ongoing action is required to address

disparities in healthcare access, provide education on pregnancy, and build support for pregnant women.

Therefore, this study will assess a mother's compliance with the Safe Motherhood program, identify factors associated with compliance and institute evidence-based services for enhancing maternal and child health. This study will help design effective interventions to promote safer pregnancy, reduce maternal mortality, and improve both mothers' and newborns' health by identifying barriers to the utilization of health services and plugging gaps in services for mothers.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent to which mothers are compliant with the Safe Motherhood Program implemented in Level II government hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. The researchers of this study aimed to assess maternal compliance with the program's components, analyze how demographic factors influence this compliance, and propose a maternal health education program to improve outcomes.

Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What are the profile variables of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Civil status;
 - 1.3 Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 Monthly family income;
 - 1.5 Occupation;
 - 1.6 Number of children;
 - 1.7 Number of prenatal check-ups during pregnancy;
 - 1.8 Number of deliveries in the hospital; and
 - 1.9 Proximity of the house to the hospital?
2. What is the extent of compliance of mothers with the Safe Motherhood Program in terms of:
 - 2.1 Antenatal care;
 - 2.2 Labor and delivery;
 - 2.3 Postpartum care;
 - 2.4 Family planning; and
 - 2.5 Health education and counseling?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent to which mothers comply with the Safe Motherhood Program based on their profile variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of mothers' compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program and their profile variables?
5. What maternal health education program could be proposed to improve the compliance of mothers with the Safe Motherhood Program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Strategy

This study employs an ex post facto, one-shot case study design using a descriptive research method to assess women's awareness and compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program. The ex post facto design is a non-experimental approach that retrospectively examines pre-existing conditions or events without manipulating variables. This design is instrumental when ethical or practical constraints prevent direct experimentation, making it a valuable tool in social and health research (Em, 2024).

A one-shot case study involves collecting data at a single point without pre-tests or control groups. Since the Safe Motherhood Program had already been implemented, this study evaluates its impact based on participants' self-reported experiences. While this design does not establish direct causation, it provides critical insights into patterns of awareness and compliance.

The study adopts a descriptive research method appropriate for identifying traits, frequencies, trends, and categories (McCombes, 2019). A questionnaire is the primary data collection tool, allowing the researcher to gather demographic information, assess participants' perceptions, and analyze the program's potential impact. Additionally, descriptive research enables comparison, classification, interpretation, and evaluation, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the findings.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study involved mothers undergoing consultations and delivery in selected Level II government hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. It will involve 60 mothers who have attended consultations and delivered at Level II government hospitals. The study was conducted during the First semester of 2024-2025.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on the DOH Manual on Safe Motherhood to obtain responses from the respondents. Part one of the questionnaire included the respondents' profiles, covering age, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, occupation, number of children, number of hospital deliveries, and proximity of the house to the hospital.

Part two addressed mothers' compliance with the safe motherhood program, encompassing antenatal care, labor and delivery, postpartum care, health education and counseling, and family planning. The questions were adapted from the DOH Manual on Safe Motherhood.

The questionnaire was utilized to gather data from the respondents. The items found in the questionnaire were taken from several articles and research studies related to mothers' compliance with safe motherhood. However, it was subjected to validation by

experts in maternal and child nursing, specifically a faculty researcher, an instructor teaching maternal and child nursing, and OB ward nurses, who used the validation instrument developed by Oducado (2020). The combined rating was highly valid.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers were granted permission by the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study. The mothers were granted informed consent prior to the data collection. Data gathering was scheduled based on the participants' availability and convenience during the first semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. The researcher safeguarded and secured personal information obtained during data collection following the Data Privacy Act (Republic Act No. 10173).

Treatment of Data

The data collected was tabulated into a contingency table and analyzed using proper statistical tools.

Frequency and percentage were used for problem number 1 to determine the profile variables, including age, civil status, highest educational status, monthly family income, number of children, occupation, number of prenatal check-ups during pregnancy, and number of deliveries in the hospital, as well as the proximity of the house to the hospital. The formula is as follows:

$$P (\%) = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where,

P = percentage equivalent to each bracket

F = number of respondents in each bracket

N = total number of respondents

The weighted mean was used for Problem 2, which assessed compliance with the safe motherhood program. The formula is as follows:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fX}{N}$$

Where,

WM = average of each category

f = number of respondents in each bracket

X = point value classification

N = total number of respondents

Part II on the extent of compliance of mothers on safe motherhood program, a five-point Likert Scale was used in the analysis as follows,

Literal Value	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Very Extensive
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Extensive
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Extensive
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Extensive
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Extensive

The Analysis of Variance was utilized to evaluate the differences in mothers' adherence to the Safe Motherhood program alongside their profile variables for problems 3 and 4, which are components of the comparative and correlational study aimed at determining the relationships and distinctions. The Pearson Coefficient Correlation was utilized to assess the relationship between variables.

Analysis of Variance

$$F = \frac{MSb}{MSw}$$

Where,

MSb = Mean Square Between

MSw = Mean Square Within

Pearson Correlation

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where,

r = Pearson correlation coefficient

x = Values in the first set of data

y = Values in the second set of data

n = Total number of values.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This study focused on assessing the extent of compliance of mothers with the Safe Motherhood Program in selected Level II government hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. It specifically examined mothers who had undergone consultations and deliveries during the first semester of the academic year 2024–2025.

The scope of the research was limited to the following key components of the Safe Motherhood Program: antenatal care, labor and delivery, postpartum care, family planning, and health education and counseling. These components were assessed through a validated survey questionnaire based on the Department of Health (DOH) Manual on Safe Motherhood.

The respondents of the study were 60 mothers who accessed maternal services from Level II government hospitals within the specified locale. Variables considered in the analysis included respondents' age, civil status, educational attainment, occupation, monthly family income, number of children, number of prenatal visits, number of hospital deliveries, and proximity of their residence to the hospital.

The delimitations of the study include its non-experimental, descriptive research design using a one-shot case study approach. Since the study used self-reported data from mothers after receiving care, causality cannot be inferred. Furthermore, the study did not cover private hospitals or healthcare centers, nor did it include women who did not utilize hospital-based maternity services. The researchers also acknowledge that findings may not be generalizable to other regions in the Philippines due to contextual differences in healthcare access and resources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Respondent's Profile

Table 1 lists the respondents' characteristics in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, occupation, number of prenatal check-ups during pregnancy, number of children, and proximity of the house to the health facility.

Age. The table shows that the majority of the respondents are in the 20-39 age bracket, with a frequency of 46 or 76.7 percent, followed by 40-59 years old, with a frequency of 8 or 13.3 percent, and 17-19 years old, with a frequency of 6 or 10 percent. This indicates that the respondents were in the young adulthood stage. According to Erik Ericson, this stage is marked by a focus on forming meaningful relationships, marriage, and family life.

Civil status. Most respondents were married, with a frequency of 41 or 68.3 percent, followed by singles, with a frequency of 19 or 31.7 percent. It showed that the respondents are in marital relationships having their own families.

Highest educational attainment. The majority of the participants held Bachelor's degrees, with a frequency of 28 or 46.7 percent; high school graduates, with a frequency of 22 or 36.7 percent; elementary graduates, with a frequency of 6 or 10 percent; and master's degree holders and vocational graduates, with a frequency of 2 or 3.3 percent. This implied that the respondents had finished their tertiary level of education.

Monthly family income. It revealed that most of the respondents' families earn a monthly income of Php 10,957 - P21,914 with a frequency of 24 or 40%; below Php 10,000 with a frequency of 23, or 38.3%, Php 21,914 - P43,828, with a frequency of 10 or 16.7%, and Php 76,669 - P131,484 with a frequency of 3, or 5%. It revealed that most respondents fall under the poor and low-income categories, highlighting economic struggles among many households. According to the National Economic Development Authority (NEDA), the most recent data comes from a 2022 survey by the Philippine Statistics Authority, which places the average wage at Php 18,423.

Occupation. Most respondents, 31, or equivalent to 51.7%, were unemployed, and those employed 29, or 48.3%. This shows that the respondents were not employed due to their responsibilities as housewives and mothers.

Number of prenatal check-ups during pregnancy. It revealed that most of the respondents undergo check-ups 5 times and more during pregnancy, with a frequency of 25 or 41.7%, followed by 1-2 times, with a frequency of 22, or 36.7%, and 3-4 times, with a frequency of 13 or 21.7%. It showed that most respondents follow the prescribed number of prenatal visits during pregnancy. According to the Department of Health, antenatal or prenatal care in the Philippines is a mandatory health service the government

provides, which recommends every pregnant woman have at least four prenatal care visits during her pregnancy. Pregnant women are offered standard services such as physical assessment (vital signs, BMI, and fundic height); laboratory screening for hepatitis, syphilis, complete blood count, and urinalysis; birth planning; and care provisions such as iron and folate supplements and tetanus toxoid immunization.

Table 1.
Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables (n=60)

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
17 – 19	6	10.0
20 – 39	46	76.7
40 – 59	8	13.3
Civil Status		
Single	19	31.7
Married	41	68.3
Highest Educational Attainment		
Elementary graduate	6	10.0
High school graduate	22	36.7
Vocational level	2	3.3
Bachelor's Degree	28	46.7
Masters units	2	3.3
Monthly Family Income (in Php)		
Below 10,957	23	38.3
10,957 – 21,914	24	40.0
21,914 – 43,828	10	16.7
76,669 – 131,484	3	5.0
Occupation		
Unemployed	31	51.7
Employed	29	48.3
Number of Prenatal check-ups during pregnancy		
1 – 2	22	36.7
3 – 4	13	21.7
5 and above	25	41.7
Number of Deliveries		
1 – 2	38	63.3
3 – 4	15	25.0
5 and above	7	11.7

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Number of Children		
1	24	40.0
2	17	28.3
3	12	20.0
4 and above	7	11.7
Proximity of House to the Health Facility		
Near	26	43.3
Far	25	41.7
Very far	9	15.0

Number of deliveries in the hospital. Findings show that 63.3% (38 out of 60) of the respondents had 1-2 deliveries in the hospital, 25.0% (15 out of 60) had 3-4 deliveries, and 11.7% (7 out of 60) had five or more deliveries. It indicates that most mothers prefer institutional deliveries, ensuring a safer childbirth experience. However, the presence of respondents with multiple home deliveries suggests that some barriers, such as accessibility, financial constraints, or personal beliefs, may prevent institutional births. Healthcare providers should strengthen outreach programs to encourage more hospital deliveries, ensuring maternal and neonatal safety.

Number of children. The survey showed that most respondents had one child, with a frequency of 24, or 40%; two (2) children, with a frequency of 17, or 28.3%; three (3) children, with a frequency of 12, or 20%; and four (4) children, with a frequency of 7, or 11.7%. Thus, the survey revealed that most respondents had few children.

Proximity of house to the health facility. It can be gleaned that most respondents are near the health facility with a frequency of 26, or 43.3%; far, with a frequency of 25, or 41.7%; and very far, with a frequency of 9, or 15%. It implies that most respondents reside near healthcare facilities.

II. Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program

Table 2 depicts the extent of mothers' compliance with safe motherhood programs, including prenatal care.

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators are rated “Extensively Compliant.” However, the highest indicators are items numbers 9 and 10, “report and go to the nearest healthcare facility if I experience any illness, especially the danger signs of pregnancy,” and “share my comprehensive past obstetric history, present to determine to estimate gestational age and my expected date of delivery correctly,” with a weighted mean of 4.12, and 4.18, or “Extensively Compliant.” It revealed that the respondents go to the health center in cases where they experience untoward manifestations during pregnancy. According to the CDC (2023), planned pregnancy, appropriate prenatal care, prevention

of complications when possible, and early and effective treatment of complications are all essential to maternal care.

Table 2.
Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Antenatal Care (n=60)

Indicators	WM	DE
1. visit the health center for my booking visits and subsequent visits to confirm my pregnancy	4.03	E
2. undergo comprehensive physical examinations	3.98	E
3. submit for laboratory examinations and other investigations	4.05	E
4. submit for check-ups to identify existing or potential problem that may affect my pregnancy	3.97	E
5. submit for comprehensive history taking by the health worker	4.03	E
6. follow scheduled visits when complications are encountered for close monitoring and time management	4.07	E
7. comply if they determined that my pregnancy requires routine or specialized care and plan for continuity care	4.05	E
8. report existing potential problems identified which can adversely affects my pregnancy and childbirth	4.03	E
9. share my comprehensive past obstetric history, present to determine estimate gestational age and my expected date of delivery correctly	4.12	E
10. report and go to the nearest healthcare facility if I experience any illness especially the danger signs of pregnancy	4.18	E
Average Weighted Mean	4.05	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

Overall, the Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Antenatal Care got an average weighted mean of 4.05, or “Extensively Compliant.” It connotes that the respondents underwent antenatal care during pregnancy. The Safe Motherhood Program provides Filipino women access to quality healthcare for a safer pregnancy and delivery. It seeks to enhance the health and well-being of mothers within

a Filipino family. The program is dedicated to provide logical and responsive policy guidance to its local government partners in delivering high-quality maternity and newborn health care with integrity and accountability using established and innovative methods (DOH, 2023).

Table 3 shows the extent of compliance of mothers to the safe motherhood program during labor and delivery.

Table 3.
Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Labor and Delivery (n=60)

Indicators	WM	DE
1. submit for physical and abdominal examinations	4.43	E
2. have undergone internal and vaginal examinations during labor and delivery	4.48	E
3. report to the healthcare facility once signs of labor were experienced	4.45	E
4. inform the healthcare provider my complete antenatal care history including the complications of my pregnancy that was detected	4.42	E
5. know that I need to inform the healthcare worker if I experience profuse bleeding, reduced fetal movement, severe headache and visual disturbance	4.48	E
6. report to my healthcare provider when my bag of water ruptured	4.40	E
7. complied with the orders of the healthcare provider especially in the progress of my labor	4.43	E
8. submit for vital signs, contractions, and labor monitoring	4.43	E
9. submit myself when they perform vaginal examination every 4 hours otherwise indicated	4.33	E
10. submit for proper positioning and other procedure during delivery	4.40	E
Average Weighted Mean	4.43	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators are rated extensively “Extensively Compliant”. However, the highest indicators are items numbers 2 and 5, “have undergone internal and vaginal examinations during labor and delivery,” and “know that I need to inform the healthcare worker if I experience profuse bleeding, reduced fetal movement,

severe headache, and visual disturbance,” with a weighted mean of 4.12, and 4.18, or “Extensively Compliant.” It revealed that the respondents submitted to the necessary examinations to prevent complications from arising. Every year, hundreds of thousands of women die or suffer serious complications from pregnancy and childbirth. Safe motherhood starts prior to conception with adequate nutrition and a healthy lifestyle (Tulchinsky, 2023).

The lowest indicator is item number 9, "submit myself when they perform vaginal examination every 4 hours," with a weighted mean of 4.33 or "Extensively Compliant.". It likely reflects lower comfort, willingness, or acceptance among respondents.

Overall, the Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program along labor and delivery got an average weighted mean of 4.05, or "Extensively Compliant. It implies that the respondents comply with the program on labor and delivery. Compliance with safe motherhood during labor and delivery refers to following established medical practices and guidelines to ensure a woman's safety and well-being throughout the birthing process, including access to qualified healthcare providers, proper monitoring of maternal and fetal health, timely intervention for complications, and appropriate post-delivery care, ultimately aiming to prevent maternal mortality and morbidity.

Table 4 shows the extent of mothers' compliance with the safe motherhood program along postpartum.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are item number 5, "practice breastfeeding right after delivery," with a weighted mean of 4.62, or "Very Extensively Compliant." It revealed that the respondents knew the benefits of breastfeeding a newborn baby. The National Institute of Health (2020) states that suckling during breastfeeding triggers the release of oxytocin from brain nerves, which promotes physiological and psychological changes essential for nursing and parenthood. Oxytocin facilitates the secretion of prolactin and the synthesis of milk (Moberg, 2020).

Table 4.
Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Post-partum (n=60)

Indicators	WM	DE
1. empty my bladder frequently after delivery	4.07	E
2. palpate and massage my uterus every 15 minutes for two hours as instructed	4.20	E
3. submit for vital signs monitoring after delivery	4.45	E
4. watch out for post-partum complications or bleeding as advised	4.40	E
5. practice breastfeeding right after delivery	4.62	VE
6. perform post-partum exercises as instructed	4.25	E
7. practice safer sex and follow when to resume my sexual relationship with my partner	4.25	E

8. take iron and folate supplement for six months after delivery	4.32	E
9. undergo post-partum check-up to maintain my health	4.30	E
10. follow what is advised about my fertility plans and submitted for counselling on the use of contraceptives	4.23	E
Average Weighted Mean	4.31	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

The lowest indicators are item 1, "empty my bladder frequently after delivery," with a weighted mean of 4.07, or "Extensively Compliant." This showed that the respondents knew the importance of emptying the bladder after delivery since it gives a feeling of comfort after the bladder is emptied. Voiding must be encouraged and monitored to prevent asymptomatic bladder overfilling (Gonzalez & Kopparapo, 2022).

Overall, the Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program along postpartum got an average weighted mean of 4.31, or "Extensively Compliant." The postpartum phase starts shortly after childbirth, often lasting for 6 to 8 weeks, concluding when the mother's body has almost reverted to its pre-pregnant condition. The weeks following birth lay the foundation of long-term health and well-being for the woman and her infant. Effective postpartum care is mandatory to improve both the mother's and newborn's short-term and long-term health consequences (Gonzalez & Kopparapo, 2022).

Table 5 shows the extent of compliance of mothers to safe motherhood programs along with family planning.

Table 5.
Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Family Planning (n=60)

Indicators	WM	DE
1. undergo family planning orientation and counselling in the healthcare facility	4.02	E
2. had the freedom to choose my contraceptive to use	4.38	E
3. take extra care on using the contraceptive for best results in preventing pregnancy	4.17	E
4. visit the healthcare facility for proper instruction on contraceptive use and its effects	4.08	E

5. involve my husband in the selection of family planning method to use	3.97	E
6. follow the advice on regular check-up while using the contraceptive	4.17	E
7. submit for consultation when side effects are felt	4.12	E
8. follow the instruction of the health care worker on the use of contraceptive and report immediately when symptoms are felt	4.15	E
9. maintain a regular supply of the contraceptive taken from the health care institution	4.13	E
10. discontinue using the contraceptive once I am ready to get pregnant with the advice of the health worker	4.17	E
Average Weighted Mean	4.14	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated “Extensively Compliant”; however, the highest indicators are item number 2, "had the freedom to choose my contraceptive to use," with a weighted mean of 4.38, or "Extensively Compliant." The postpartum period is an ideal time to access contraception services, as patients are known not to be pregnant, may be motivated to initiate contraception, and are under the care of clinicians with the appropriate expertise. Counselling involves understanding a patient's wishes regarding future pregnancy, their preferences regarding contraceptive options, and the characteristics and attributes of the contraceptive methods themselves (Sonalkar & Mody, 2025).

The lowest indicators are item 5, "involve my husband in the selection of family planning method to use," with a weighted mean of 3.97, or "Extensively Compliant." This shows that the role of the husband in contraceptive use is vital. According to Sonalkar and Mody (2025), a father's involvement in contraceptive use can positively impact a couple's sexual and reproductive health. It can also help shape a young man's attitude toward sexual responsibility.

Overall, the Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program, along with family planning, got an average weighted mean of 4.14, or "Extensively Compliant." The responders demonstrated adherence to the family planning guidelines of the Safe Motherhood initiative. As stated by Allman et al. (2023), women's choices about family planning (FP) are shaped by social norms, which are the implicit guidelines governing acceptable behavior within social networks. They are influenced by guidance and

information from pivotal figures who determine what is deemed acceptable inside the family.

Table 6 shows the extent to which mothers comply with the safe motherhood program on antenatal health education and counselling.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are items number 1, 8, 9, and 10, "follow the advice of the health worker on proper nutrition and breastfeeding," "follow health care advice on the importance of preventing infection and personal hygiene" "follow exclusive breastfeeding for my baby," and "prepare and clean my breast before breastfeeding my baby as advised by healthcare worker" with a weighted mean of 4.50, 4.53, 4.57, and 4.60, or "Very Extensively Compliant." It implies that the respondents knew the importance of proper nutrition after delivery for breastfeeding the infant. Breast milk contains necessary antibodies that protect the baby from childhood illnesses. The National Institute of Health (2020) states that breastfeeding facilitates contact and bonding between mother and newborn. An extended length of breastfeeding correlated with increased mother sensitive response, enhanced attachment security, and reduced attachment disorganization in the infant.

Table 6.
Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program Along Antenatal Health Education and Counseling (n=60)

Indicators	WM	DE
1. follow the advises of the health worker on proper nutrition and breastfeeding	4.53	VE
2. follow healthy lifestyle during pregnancy and postpartum as instructed by healthcare worker	4.32	E
3. follow birth preparedness and complications readiness as instructed by healthcare worker	4.17	E
4. listen on the basic information about some minor discomforts during pregnancy and will go to nearest healthcare facility when needed	4.18	E
5. plan to deliver in a healthcare facility because I was instructed the importance of facility-based delivery	4.33	E
6. follow the health workers advise on immunization of my baby	4.48	E
7. practice infant feeding and advise on problems that may arise like sore nipples, inadequate breast milk and others	4.45	E
8. follow health care advise on the importance of preventing infection and personal hygiene	4.50	VE
9. follow exclusive breastfeeding for my baby	4.57	VE
10. prepare and clean my breast before breastfeeding my baby as advised by healthcare worker	4.60	VE
Average Weighted Mean	4.41	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

The lowest indicators are item numbers 3 and 4, "follow birth preparedness and complications readiness as instructed by a healthcare worker," "listen on the oriented basic information about some minor discomforts during pregnancy and will go to the nearest healthcare facility when needed," with a weighted mean of 4.17 and 4.18, or "Extensively Compliant." It showed that the respondents internalized the health teachings given by the health providers necessary for the well-being of the mother and child.

Overall, the Extent of mothers' Compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program, along with antenatal health education and counselling, got an average weighted mean of 4.41, or "Extensively Compliant." It revealed that mothers agreed on the importance of antenatal health education and counselling as a guide for a healthy mother and baby.

Table 7 summarizes the extent of mothers' compliance with the safe motherhood program.

As gleaned from the table, all the aspects are rated "Extensively Compliant". However, the highest is on the aspects of antenatal health education and counselling and labor and delivery, with a weighted mean of 4.41 and 4.43, or "Extensively Compliant." It clearly showed that this area is appreciated by mothers for their safety and well-being, for a healthy mother and baby, and for being free from complications after delivery. Health education for pregnant mothers includes information about nutrition, exercise, hygiene, and prenatal care. The research conducted by Rasheed and Alshoweliem (2023) on health education requirements during pregnancy revealed that several women have substantial knowledge of certain health concerns, including the dietary consumption of vital nutrients such as dairy products. The research on health education was corroborated.

The lowest aspect is antenatal care, with a weighted mean of 4.05, or "Extensively Compliant." Although this aspect is the lowest, mothers still comply with antenatal care during pregnancy. Undergoing a prenatal check-up is a must for pregnant women for a safer pregnancy and delivery.

Table 7.
Summary on the Extent of Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood Program (n=60)

Aspect	WM	DE
Antenatal Care	4.05	E

Labor and Delivery	4.43	E
Post-partum	4.31	E
Family Planning	4.14	E
Health Education and Counseling	4.41	E
Overall Weighted Mean	4.27	E

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Very Extensive (VE)
3.50 – 4.49	Extensive (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Extensive (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Extensive (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Extensive (NE)

Overall, the summary on the Extent of mothers' Compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program got an overall weighted mean of 4.27, or "Extensively Compliant." It revealed that the program is implemented well in the said locality; however, an intensified implementation will still be done to make them very extensively compliant.

III. Difference Between the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Programs and Their Profile Variables

Table 8 presents the difference in the extent of mothers' compliance with safe motherhood across ages.

The ANOVA findings indicated no significant changes in prenatal care, labor and delivery, and postpartum outcomes. This means that mothers are extensively compliant to the same extent in these areas regardless of their age.

Table 8.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	3.133	2	1.566	2.211	.119	Not Significant
	Within Groups	40.377	57	.708			
	Total	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	1.580	2	.790	1.476	.237	Not Significant
	Within Groups	30.493	57	.535			
	Total	32.073	59				

Post-partum	Between Groups	1.703	2	.852	2.326	.107	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.881	57	.366			
	Total	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	5.009	2	2.505	5.255	.008	Significant
	Within Groups	27.167	57	.477			
	Total	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	2.633	2	1.316	4.702	.013	Significant
	Within Groups	15.957	57	.280			
	Total	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	2.634	2	1.317	4.557	.015	Significant
	Within Groups	16.470	57	.289			
	Total	19.104	59				

Nonetheless, significant differences are seen in family planning, health education, and counselling. Results indicate the need for further testing to identify the groups exhibiting significant differences.

Table 9 displays the results of the Scheffe test for significant age differences. The test indicated a significant disparity in mothers' adherence to family planning based on age groupings.

Table 9.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Age

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Family Planning	17-19 vs 20-39	-.926	.012
Overall Extent of compliance	17-19 vs 20-39	-.627	.034

Specifically, the 20-39 age group has a higher extent of compliance than the younger age group, 17 – 19. This has affected the overall results, suggesting that the overall extent of mothers' compliance with safe motherhood differs significantly across ages. It revealed that younger mothers still need to be more knowledgeable about the program to be more compliant. At a young age, they need a lot of health education to have a healthier pregnancy in their subsequent pregnancies.

Table 10 presents the difference in the extent to which mothers comply with safe motherhood programs across civil statuses.

Table 10.
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Civil Status

Aspect	Civil Status	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Single	19	3.48	-.830	.214	58	-3.877	.000	Significant
	Married	41	4.31						
Labor and Delivery	Single	19	4.33	-.137	.206	58	-.665	.509	Not Significant
	Married	41	4.47						
Post-partum	Single	19	4.32	.011	.173	58	.063	.950	Not Significant
	Married	41	4.30						
Family Planning	Single	19	3.73	-.590	.192	58	-3.081	.003	Significant
	Married	41	4.32						
Health Education and Counseling	Single	19	4.16	-.374	.149	58	-2.505	.015	Significant
	Married	41	4.53						
Overall Extent of Compliance	Single	19	4.00	-.384	.151	58	-2.542	.014	Significant
	Married	41	4.39						

Based on computed t-values, no significant difference exists between labor, delivery, and post-partum. Meanwhile, Significant differences exist in antenatal care, family planning, health education, and counselling, as well as in the overall extent of compliance of the mothers. The significant negative mean differences indicate that the second group, that is, the married mothers, have been more compliant with the safe motherhood program as compared to the single mothers. It revealed that the married

ones were more mature in understanding the aspects of the program than the young ones, which may be due to inadequate knowledge of parenting a baby.

Table 11 displays the difference in the extent to which mothers comply with the safe motherhood program across the highest educational attainment.

Table 11.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	17.100	4	4.275	8.903	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	26.409	55	.480			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	4.716	4	1.179	2.370	.064	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.357	55	.497			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	1.751	4	.438	1.155	.341	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.835	55	.379			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	11.123	4	2.781	7.264	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	21.054	55	.383			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	4.179	4	1.045	3.987	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	14.410	55	.262			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	4.691	4	1.173	4.475	.003	Significant
	Within Groups	14.413	55	.262			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

Based on the computed F-values, no significant difference exists along labor, delivery, and post-partum. Considerable differences are detected along antenatal care, family planning, health education, and the overall extent of compliance of the mothers—the results of the Scheffe test are shown in the following table.

The overall extent of compliance of the mothers, the groups that have finished higher levels of education have been more compliant with the Safe Motherhood program. It again revealed that mothers with more education were more appreciative of the safe motherhood program than the younger ones. Therefore, young mothers must be well-oriented on the program and its benefits to them and their children.

Table 12 reveals the groups that differ significantly in compliance with the Safe Motherhood program when grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Table 12.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal care	Elem grad vs HS grad	-1.089	.029
	Elem grad vs voc level	-1.817	.047
	Elem grad vs Bachelor's degree	-1.742	.000
	HS grad vs Bachelor's degree	-.652	.038
Family Planning	Elem grad vs HS grad	-.950	.036
	Elem grad vs Bachelor's degree	-1.443	.000
Health Education and Counseling	Elem grad vs Bachelor's degree	-.781	.031
Overall Extent of Compliance	Elem grad vs Bachelor's degree	-.793	.027
	HS grad vs Bachelor's degree	-.471	.045

Significant negative mean differences are shown; hence, the second group in each group has provided higher mean values. This implies that in terms of antenatal care, family planning, health education, and the overall extent of mothers' compliance, the groups that have finished higher levels of education have been more compliant with the safe motherhood program. The younger mothers must attend a reorientation of the program to fully understand the coverage and improve their knowledge of pregnancy and child care.

Table 13 shows the difference in the extent of compliance with the Safe Motherhood program across monthly family income.

Table 13.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Monthly Family Income

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	11.034	3	3.678	6.343	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	32.475	56	.580			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	1.192	3	.397	.720	.544	Not Significant
	Within Groups	30.881	56	.551			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	.613	3	.204	.521	.670	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.973	56	.392			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	7.435	3	2.478	5.609	.002	Significant
	Within Groups	24.742	56	.442			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	2.645	3	.882	3.097	.034	Significant
	Within Groups	15.944	56	.285			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	3.292	3	1.097	3.886	.014	Significant
	Within Groups	15.812	56	.282			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

No significant difference exists between labor and delivery and post-partum. The mothers have shown considerable differences regarding income in the remaining areas, namely antenatal care, family planning, and health education. The results of the Scheffe test are displayed in the following table. It implies that the mothers with higher monthly family income were more compliant, particularly on prenatal, contraception, and health education. It is, therefore, the focus of educating them on the necessity of undergoing check-ups to gain more information on the importance of the program for a healthier mother and child.

Table 14 confirms that the extent to which mothers comply with antenatal care and family planning is significantly different when grouped according to monthly family income.

Table 14.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Monthly Family Income

Aspect	Compared Groups				Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal Care	Below 10,957	vs	10,957-		-.774	.011
	21,914					
Family Panning	Below 10,957	vs	21,914-		-.978	.014
	43,828					
Family Panning	Below 10,957	vs	10,957-		-.675	.011
	21,914					

The negative mean differences indicate that mothers with higher monthly incomes comply more with safe motherhood programs, particularly antenatal care and family planning. Therefore, health workers focus on involving younger mothers in prenatal care and the use of contraception after delivery. Regardless of their income, mothers must be well informed about the benefits they get from the safe motherhood program.

Table 15 presents the findings of the analysis of the variance in mothers' adherence to the safe motherhood program across different occupations.

No significant difference exists between labor and delivery and post-partum. This means that the extent of compliance of unemployed and employed mothers is the same in these aspects. Meanwhile, a significant difference exists in antenatal care, family planning, and health education and counselling. It also led to substantial differences in mothers' compliance with the Safe Motherhood program. The significant negative mean differences indicate that the employed mothers claimed they are more compliant with the safe motherhood programs, antenatal care, family planning, and health education than the unemployed mothers.

Table 15.
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Occupation

Aspect	Occupation	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Unemployed	31	3.74	-.647	.207	58	-3.128	.003	Significant
	Employed	29	4.39						
Labor and Delivery	Unemployed	31	4.37	-.118	.191	58	-.619	.539	Not Significant
	Employed	29	4.49						
Postpartum	Unemployed	31	4.24	-.151	.160	58	-.942	.350	Not Significant
	Employed	29	4.39						
Family Planning	Unemployed	31	3.82	-.660	.172	58	-3.840	.000	Significant
	Employed	29	4.48						
Health Education and Counseling	Unemployed	31	4.26	-.308	.141	58	-2.191	.033	Significant
	Employed	29	4.57						
Overall Extent of Compliance	Unemployed	31	4.08	-.377	.140	58	-2.696	.009	Significant
	Employed	29	4.46						

Table 16 displays the difference in the extent to which mothers comply with the Safe Motherhood program across the number of prenatal check-ups during pregnancy.

The computed F-values in all aspects under consideration indicate significant results. Hence, there is a substantial difference in the extent of compliance of the mothers when several prenatal check-ups are considered. The results of the Scheffe test are shown in the succeeding table. It implies that mothers who had undergone more antenatal check-ups during pregnancy were more familiar with the program, so their attendance was more visible than those who escaped check-ups.

Table 16.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Prenatal Check-ups during Pregnancy

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	14.042	2	7.021	13.580	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	29.468	57	.517			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	3.900	2	1.950	3.945	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	28.172	57	.494			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	3.384	2	1.692	5.023	.010	Significant
	Within Groups	19.202	57	.337			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	7.803	2	3.901	9.123	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	24.374	57	.428			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	4.987	2	2.493	10.448	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	13.603	57	.239			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	6.262	2	3.131	13.898	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	12.842	57	.225			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

Table 17 shows the verified significant difference in the different areas through the Scheffe Test.

Table 17.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Prenatal Check-ups during Pregnancy

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal Care	1-2 vs 5 & above	-.974	.000
	3-4 vs 5 & above	-.993	.001
Postpartum	1-2 vs 5 & above	-.456	.033
	3-4 vs 5 & above	-.519	.040
Family Planning	1-2 vs 5 & above	-.696	.003
	3-4 vs 5 & above	-.783	.004
Health Education & Counseling	1-2 vs 5 & above	-.647	.000
	3-4 vs 5 & above	-.669	.001

Overall Extent of Compliance	1-2 vs 5 & above	-.647	.000
	3-4 vs 5 & above	-.669	.001

The negative mean differences along antenatal care, post-partum, family planning, and health education indicate that mothers undergoing more check-ups during pregnancy are more compliant with the safe motherhood program. The mothers who attended religiously to the program's activities were more informed and compliant with the program. Again, the role of the healthcare workers is to follow up with the mothers who fail or escape, attending check-ups and visits to the healthcare facility.

Table 18.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Deliveries

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	5.104	2	2.552	3.788	.029	Significant
	Within Groups	38.406	57	.674			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	.523	2	.261	.472	.626	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.550	57	.554			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	.907	2	.453	1.192	.311	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.679	57	.380			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	.932	2	.466	.851	.433	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.244	57	.548			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	1.284	2	.642	2.114	.130	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.306	57	.304			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	.888	2	.444	1.390	.257	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.216	57	.320			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

Table 18 presents the difference in the extent to which mothers comply with the safe motherhood program across the number of deliveries.

The negative mean differences along antenatal care, post-partum, family planning, and health education indicate that mothers undergoing more check-ups during pregnancy are more compliant with the safe motherhood program. The mothers who attended religiously to the program's activities were more informed and compliant with the program.

Again, the role of the healthcare workers is to follow up with the mothers who fail or escape, attending check-ups and visits to the healthcare facility.

A significant difference is shown only in antenatal care, as indicated in the computed F-value, and the significance value is lower than the set .05 level of significance. It revealed that mothers with fewer children had complied with the Safe Motherhood program. This might be related to the fact that those with more children had inadequate time to visit the healthcare facility and thereby will be advised to do so.

Table 19 confirms that there is a significant difference in antenatal care when the mothers are grouped according to the number of deliveries.

Table 19.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Deliveries

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal Care	1-2 vs 3-4	.662	.037

The positive mean difference between 1-2 and 3-4 deliveries implies that the mothers with fewer deliveries were more compliant with antenatal care. It further revealed that those with fewer children were more willing to comply with the program, probably because they were more convinced of the importance of the safe motherhood program.

Table 20 presents the difference in the extent to which mothers comply with the safe motherhood program across the number of children.

The table shows no significant difference in labor and delivery, postpartum, family planning, or health education. Only antenatal care indicates a significant difference across the number of children.

Table 20.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Children

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	6.458	3	2.153	3.254	.028	Significant
	Within Groups	37.052	56	.662			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	1.283	3	.428	.778	.511	Not Significant
	Within Groups	30.790	56	.550			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	.880	3	.293	.757	.523	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.706	56	.388			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	2.353	3	.784	1.473	.232	Not Significant
	Within Groups	29.824	56	.533			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	2.280	3	.760	2.609	.060	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.310	56	.291			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	1.651	3	.550	1.766	.164	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.453	56	.312			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

Table 21 reveals the Scheffe Test results indicating a significant difference in mothers' compliance with antenatal care between mothers with 2 and 3 children.

Table 21.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Number of Children

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal Care	2 vs 3	.896	.046

The positive mean difference implies that mothers with two children have been more compliant with the safe motherhood program, particularly regarding antenatal care, than those with three children.

Table 22 displays the difference in the extent of mothers' compliance with the Safe Motherhood program across the proximity of the house to the health facility.

Table 22.
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Proximity of House to the Health Facility

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Antenatal Care	Between Groups	9.732	2	4.866	8.211	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	33.778	57	.593			
	<i>Total</i>	43.510	59				
Labor and Delivery	Between Groups	1.617	2	.808	1.513	.229	Not Significant
	Within Groups	30.456	57	.534			
	<i>Total</i>	32.073	59				
Post-partum	Between Groups	.743	2	.372	.970	.385	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.843	57	.383			
	<i>Total</i>	22.586	59				
Family Planning	Between Groups	5.153	2	2.577	5.435	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	27.023	57	.474			
	<i>Total</i>	32.177	59				
Health Education and Counseling	Between Groups	.518	2	.259	.817	.447	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.071	57	.317			
	<i>Total</i>	18.589	59				
Overall Extent of Compliance	Between Groups	2.538	2	1.269	4.366	.017	Significant
	Within Groups	16.566	57	.291			
	<i>Total</i>	19.104	59				

No significant difference exists in labor and delivery, post-partum, and health education. An important difference exists in antenatal care and family planning as well as in the overall extent of compliance of the mothers. Results of the Scheffe test to further verify the existence of significant differences and determine groups that differ across proximity to the health facility are shown in the following table.

Table 23 shows the results of the Scheffe Test, confirming that there is a significant difference in antenatal care across the proximity of the house to the health facility.

Table 23.
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program across Proximity of House to the Health Facility

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Antenatal Care	Near vs very far	1.186	.001
Overall Extent of Compliance	Near vs very far	.609	.019

The same result applies to the overall extent of compliance of the mothers. The positive mean difference suggests that mothers who live near the health facility seem

more compliant with the Safe Motherhood program than those who live very far from the facility. This implies that mothers residing near healthcare facilities have higher compliance rates than those who live far away. It might be related to the fact that those far away need more time and finances than those within walking distance of the health facility.

IV. Relationship Between the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Programs and Their Profile Variables

Table 24 shows the significant relationship between the extent to which mothers are compliant with safe motherhood and their profile variables.

Compliance with prenatal care is positively correlated with proximity to healthcare facilities, elevated educational levels, increased monthly family income, and a greater number of checks, while concurrently exhibiting less births among working married women.

Table 24.
Relationship Between the Extent of Compliance of Mothers on Safe Motherhood Program and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Antenatal Care		Labor and Delivery		Post-partum		Family Planning		Health Education and Counseling	
	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig
Age	.032	.806	.035	.788	.078	.554	.138	.292	-.008	.952
Civil Status	.454*	.000	.087	.509	-.008	.950	.375*	.003	.312*	.015
Highest educational Attainment	.522*	.000	.144	.274	.068	.606	.463*	.000	.384*	.002
Monthly Family Income	.464*	.000	.183	.163	.141	.282	.428*	.001	.342*	.008
Occupation	.380*	.003	.081	.539	.123	.350	.450*	.000	.276*	.033
Number of Prenatal Checkups	.513*	.000	.295*	.022	.334*	.009	.427*	.001	.504*	.000

Number of Deliveries	-.276*	.033	.058	.659	.139	.289	-.145	.270	-.111	.397
Number of Children	-.248	.056	.085	.518	.073	.578	-.143	.277	-.181	.167
Proximity of House to Health Facility	.467*	.000	-.221	.090	-.148	.260	-.366*	.004	-.164	.212

***Significant at .05 level**

Compliance with prenatal care is positively correlated with proximity to healthcare facilities, better educational attainment, increased monthly family income, and a higher number of prenatal visits, while being inversely related to the number of deliveries among working married women.

The more checkups the mothers undergo during pregnancy, the more compliant they are with the Safe Motherhood program, specifically during labor, delivery, and postpartum.

On the other hand, the higher the educational attainment, monthly family income, and number of prenatal checkups during pregnancy of employed married mothers, the more compliant they are with the safe motherhood program, particularly regarding family planning and health education and counselling.

V. Proposed Maternal Health Program to Improve the Compliance of Mothers to Safe Motherhood

To improve compliance with safe motherhood practices, a comprehensive health education program can include specific activities across various stages of maternal health: prenatal, labor and delivery, postpartum, and family planning. Implementing these activities can significantly enhance mothers' knowledge and compliance with safe motherhood. The program can improve community maternal and neonatal health outcomes by providing comprehensive education and support. Hence, a health program with the tagline "Proficient Care and Perfect Parenting" was proposed with specific program components and activities.

The **Proficient Care and Perfect Parenting Program** aims to improve maternal and newborn health outcomes using a comprehensive health education campaign. This program will focus on six components: Prenatal Care Education, Labor and Delivery Preparation, Postpartum Support and Education, Parenting Skills and Development, Family Planning and Health Education, and Community Engagement and support. Collectively, these components create an integrated and responsive approach to maternal care, addressing both medical and psychosocial needs.

Table 25 shows the Program Guide for Proficient Care and Perfect Parenting.

Table 25.
Program Guide for Proficient Care and Perfect Parenting

Component	Objectives	Strategies	Budget (₱)	Persons Involve	Time Frame	Expected Outcome
1. Prenatal Care Education	Enhance maternal health by educating mothers on prenatal care and safe motherhood practices.	Monthly workshops on prenatal health, nutrition, and recognizing warning signs during pregnancy.	18,000	OB-GYNs, nutrition-nists, program coordina-tors.	Month 1-9 (Mont hly)	Improved maternal knowled-ge on prenatal care and reduced pregnan-cy-related risks.
2. Labor and Delivery Preparation	Prepare mothers for labor and delivery, ensuring informed decision-making and pain management.	A. Birth plan creation workshops Facilitate sessions where mothers can create personali-zed birth plans, discussing preferen-ces for labor and delivery B. Pain manageme nt sessions (breathing techniques	20,000	Midwife, OB-GYNs, birth coaches .	Birth Plan: Once in Month 6; Pain Mana ge-ment: Once in Month 7	Increased confiden- ce in labor and delivery decisions, reduced anxiety.

		and relaxation methods). Provide education on pain management options during labor, including breathing techniques, and relaxation methods				
3. Postpartum Support and Education	Support mothers in postpartum recovery and breastfeeding.	A. Postpartum Recovery Workshop Conduct workshops focused on physical and emotional recovery after childbirth, including self-care strategies and recognizing postpartum depression.	20,000	Lactation consultants, mental health professionals.	Recovery Workshop: Month 8-12 (Monthly); Breastfeeding Support Group: Month 8-12 (Weekly)	Higher breastfeeding rates, better postpartum mental health.

		<p>B. Breast-feeding Support Group</p> <p>Establish a weekly support groups for breastfeeding mothers to share experiences, and receive expert advice</p>				
4. Parenting Skills Development	Enhance parenting skills and strengthen parent-child bonds.	<p>A. Parenting classes</p> <p>Offer classes covering child development stages, effective discipline strategies, and fostering emotional intelligence in children.</p> <p>B. Interactive play sessions.</p> <p>Organize playgroups where mothers</p>	25,000	Child psychologists, parenting coaches	<p>Parenting: Month 3-12 (Monthly);</p> <p>Play Sessions: Month 4-12 (Weekly)</p>	Improved parenting confidence and stronger parent-child relationships.

		can engage in activities with their children while learning about developmental milestones				
5. Family Planning and Health Education	Educate mothers and couples about family planning and reproductive health.	Quarterly workshops on contraceptive methods and pregnancy spacing.	15,000	Family planning educators, health care providers.	Month 3, 6, 9, 12 (Quarterly)	Increased awareness and adoption of family planning practices.
6. Community Engagement and Support	Foster a supportive community for mothers.	A. Weekly support groups for mothers Establish support groups where mothers can share experiences, challenges in a safe environment B. Online resource hub with educational materials	18,000	Program facilitators, IT specialists, health-care providers.	Support Group : Month 2-12 (Weekly); Online Hub: On-going	Stronger social support networks, increased engagement with maternal resources

		and healthcare access. Create a website or social media group where mothers can access educational materials, connect with healthcare providers, and share experiences.				
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The budget created is for a single event for fifteen participants in prenatal care, labor and delivery, postpartum care, parenting, family planning, and community involvement. It is designed to minimize costs while maximizing resource use and efficiency. Each event component tackles specific issues about maternal health and is delivered by qualified professionals using adequate instructional materials.

The estimated budget for the event is ₱116,000, which covers the venue, resources, logistics, facilitator payment, teaching materials, food, and other items. All program components are appropriately funded, guaranteeing a comprehensive maternal healthcare program that achieves the desired outcome with the specific target beneficiaries.

Conclusions

In light of the findings from the study, the subsequent conclusions can be articulated.

The demographic profile of mothers, including age, civil status, education, income, occupation, number of prenatal check-ups, number of hospital deliveries, number of children, and proximity to healthcare facilities, significantly influenced their compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program. Notably, mothers who are older, married, educated, and financially stable exhibited higher adherence. Furthermore, individuals who attended more prenatal check-ups and lived closer to healthcare facilities demonstrated better

compliance, underscoring the significance of accessibility and regular monitoring in maternal health.

Moreover, mothers demonstrated high overall compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program, particularly in labor and delivery, health education, and counseling. However, compliance was lower in antenatal care, indicating the need for increased awareness and participation in prenatal check-ups. This suggests that greater emphasis should be placed on early pregnancy interventions and routine maternal healthcare to improve adherence.

In addition, significant differences in compliance were observed based on demographic variables. Young mothers, particularly those who have attained lower educational qualifications and those from lower-income groups, exhibited lower adherence. This discovery highlights the necessity for focused interventions, particularly for disadvantaged populations, to enhance compliance and improve maternal health outcomes.

Furthermore, a strong correlation was found between compliance and demographic factors. Mothers with higher education, stable employment, more prenatal visits, and higher income demonstrated greater adherence to maternal healthcare recommendations. It highlights the importance of improving socioeconomic conditions and access to healthcare to enhance participation in maternal health programs.

Therefore, a structured maternal health education program is recommended to address gaps in maternal healthcare compliance. This program should increase awareness, promote regular prenatal check-ups, and encourage family involvement in maternal health decisions. Furthermore, enhancing healthcare accessibility and executing focused educational initiatives will be essential. Strengthening maternal healthcare systems through these efforts is crucial for achieving improved health results for mothers and children.

Recommendations

After formulating the above conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

Mothers need to be encouraged to attend more prenatal check-ups for early detection and management of pregnancy-related complications. Healthcare providers must extend their reach, especially to mothers who are not able to visit healthcare facilities with ease, to ensure uniform delivery of high-quality maternal healthcare services for everyone.

Likewise, health institutions should pursue maternal health education with a greater emphasis on antenatal care. To encourage more mothers to seek these services,

increasing community awareness campaigns focused on the benefits of regular check-ups and healthy pregnancy is needed.

Moreover, programs should specifically target younger mothers, less educated, and more economically disadvantaged people. In order to guarantee that these groups have affordable access to maternal healthcare services, governmental and non-governmental organizations should collaborate to finance and encourage them to receive maternal healthcare services.

Healthcare practitioners should also prioritize mothers from low-income families and those who receive fewer prenatal visits. Expanding healthcare facilities in rural areas and reducing financial barriers through employment opportunities will enhance compliance with the Safe Motherhood Program, ensuring that more mothers receive the necessary care. Addressing socioeconomic barriers through policy advocacy will help more mothers participate in maternal health programs.

A structured maternal health education program can be adapted for implementation to improve maternal healthcare compliance. This program can improve community maternal and neonatal health outcomes by providing comprehensive education and support, enhancing maternal education, parenting skills, community support, and family well-being by encouraging healthy family dynamics and effective communication.

The study also highlights the need for further research into numerous factors that are related to and barriers to digital health solutions, healthcare access barriers, adherence barriers, and intervention methods. In order to gain further insight into trends in maternal healthcare compliance, we recommend that future research increase the sample size to include populations from a wider range of demographics, particularly those belonging to rural and low-income communities. Research should also explore how spousal support, members of a woman's family, and friends may be able to lay roles toward ensuring compliance with maternal healthcare decisions and how digital health tools, as well as telemedicine, might positively impact compliance. Moreover, the study of existing governmental policies related to maternal health care and mental health in cases of pregnancy can help form a more cohesive maternal health program, especially for those who are underprivileged, single mothers, teenagers, and more in the near future. Addressing these research gaps is essential in both providing a sound basis for maternal healthcare policy and service delivery and delivering equitable and sustainable maternal health services for all.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study strictly adhered to ethical standards in the planning, conduct, and reporting of the research. All procedures were implemented with the utmost

regard for the rights, dignity, safety, and welfare of the participants, and were aligned with established ethical research principles. The following key areas were observed:

1. Respect for Participant Autonomy

Informed consent was secured from all respondents after providing a clear explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any point without any adverse consequences or pressure.

2. Confidentiality and Privacy Protection

The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained. No identifying information was collected, and all responses were handled with sensitivity and stored securely. Only the researchers had access to the data, which was used solely for the purposes of this academic research.

3. Beneficence and Non-maleficence

The study was conducted with the intent of minimizing any form of harm. Every effort was made to protect the psychological, emotional, and physical well-being of the participants throughout the research process.

4. Transparency and Disclosure

The researchers maintained full transparency in disclosing the study's objectives, methodology, and scope. All participants were adequately informed, and the reporting of results was done truthfully and without distortion. No aspects of the research process were concealed from stakeholders or participants.

5. Fair Treatment and Equity

All participants were treated fairly and equitably, regardless of age, educational attainment, socioeconomic status, or other demographic attributes. Their participation was valued, and their voices were respected without discrimination or bias.

6. Professional Integrity

The researchers conducted the study with honesty, rigor, and objectivity. There was no fabrication, falsification, or selective reporting of data. Plagiarism was strictly

voided, and all sources of literature and data used in the study were properly acknowledged using APA citation style.

7. Participant Advocacy

Throughout the research process, the researchers advocated for the rights and welfare of all participants, ensuring that any concerns were addressed and that participants felt safe, heard, and respected.

8. Conflict of Interest Management

There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. The researchers affirm that the findings were interpreted objectively and used solely for academic and scientific purposes, with no personal or financial interest involved.

9. Use and Interpretation of Results:

The data gathered and analyzed were used purely for academic research. No commercial or exploitative purpose was pursued. Furthermore, the interpretation of findings was done without bias, ensuring the integrity and credibility of the study's conclusions.

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